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Over 36 Years of HAB Monitoring for the Aquaculture Industry: the *Plancton Andino* experience

At *Plancton Andino* we study the temporal and spatial distribution of phytoplankton, focusing on HAB species and ecological succession. Our data are used to enhance Early Warning Systems [1] and machine learning models for HAB forecasting using the HAB_f INDEX algorithm in areas of intense salmon and mollusc mariculture. The HAB_f INDEX integrates the water column by summing the ratio of each harmful algal concentration to its critical threshold, weighted by species-specific factors [2].

There is extensive knowledge about HABs, both worldwide [3–4] and locally—especially over the past eight years [5,6]—which we can access almost immediately after digital publication. Many authors assume that HABs are increasing in coastal zones, but an alternative view suggests that we are observing the ocean with greater frequency, leading to inherent bias in historical analysis. Some scientists suggest that intensified monitoring associated with increased aquaculture production may be responsible for the perceived increase in HAB events, and that there is no empirical support for increasing global upward trend. Instead, trends must be considered

regionally and at the species level [7].

During nearly four decades of monitoring, we have observed that some species have expanded geographically, possibly due to climate anomalies. Concurrently, economic impacts have increased due to the intensified use of coastal zones and their resources.

The North Sea is an area where both climate change and de-eutrophication efforts may already be apparent—specifically in phytoplankton communities—through shifts in biogeography, altered species composition, and increased biomass of HAB species [8]. Trainer et al [9] relate extreme HAB events in the Pacific Coastal Ocean, including southern Chile, to climatic anomalies. Zheng et al [10] suggest that human activity and climate change are increasingly affecting marine environments, leading to more HABs in Chinese waters.

From a technological standpoint, *Plancton Andino* has implemented digital image analysis of phytoplankton cells and real-time visualization of oceanographic data. We are moving towards *in-situ* monitoring with automated bio-imaging of plankton cells, with cloud-based archiving and visuali-

Fig. 1. The southern tip of South America encompasses the Chilean fjords and channels. Operationally, we refer to the polygon shown on the map as the Southern Chilean Marine Inlets (A). Satellite image of chl a from 4 January 2021. Credit: NASA (B). Watercolour depiction of patches of *H. akashiwo* and sill waters from a front area of Cholgo fjord and Blanco River on 17 April 2024 (C).

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Fig. 2. Number of phytoplankton samples analysed per year over the past 30 years by Plancton Andino (latest data from 2 May 2025).

zation. This technology, combined with predictive models like **BloomPredictor**—a machine learning model for forecasting the HAB_f Index—makes mitigation decisions more cost-effective and reduces risk. Our fundamental question is whether HABs, parametrized with the HAB_f INDEX algorithm, are increasing in frequency due to oceanographic-environmental shifts and/or plankton monitoring efforts. We are reviewing our database—after quality control and enhancement—to test this hypothesis, while considering specific statistical assumptions.

We have monitored and investigated under the POAS+ programme (Programa Oceanográfico y Ambiental en Salmónidos) in the Southern Chilean

Marine Inlet (SCMIn) between latitudes 41°S to 46°S. Here, we frequently collect live phytoplankton samples from fish farm sites without using fixatives (Fig. 1).

The first author has monitored the local marine phytoplankton since 1984 (Fig. 2). The earliest Phytoplankton Monitoring Program (PMP) report was issued in December 1988, following a severe brown tide caused by *Heterosigma akashiwo* that spring (Fig. 4). The initial dataset was archived in Lotus and Excel files, and since 2007 has been stored on a local server and subsequently on Azure. Figures 2 and 3 present basic data from long-term monitoring in SCMIn. Figure 2 shows the number of phytoplankton

samples from the early 1990s to date, noting that the server service began in 2007. Fig. 3 illustrates the 2016–2024 period, highlighting the number of dates per year with a HAB_f INDEX over 3; the maximum was 56 in 2016, and it dropped below 19 in 2017, 2020, and 2024. The HAB_f INDEX trend declined during this period (Figs. 3, 5). However, phytoplankton composition results show shifts in the interannual patterns of HAB species (Fig. 6), particularly after 2004, when *Pseudochattonella cf. verruculosa*, which affects salmon gills, was first detected.

Final remarks: When analysing the historical PMP data, several considerations must be taken into account. From 1982 to 2015, the number

Fig. 3. Number of dates per year with a HAB_f INDEX greater than 3. This graph avoids statistical bias, as sampling strategies have remained consistent across years.

Fig. 4. Timeline of key events over a 37-year period related to HABs in the Southern Chilean Marine Ecosystems.

Fig. 5. Maximum annual HABfINDEX in Southern Chilean time series from 2016 to 2025.

Fig. 6. Time series of cell abundances (cell/mL) in southern Chile of *A. catenella* (1996–2025) (A), *P. micans* (1983–2025) (B), *H. akashiwo* (1988–2025) (C), and *Pseudochattonella cf. verruculosa* (1988–2025) (D).

of samples collected was significantly lower than in the period from 2015 onward. This disparity is primarily due to the 2016 HAB events, which prompted the implementation of a more consistent and frequent sampling strategy. As a result, differences in temporal and spatial sampling effort

introduce an inherent bias in historical comparisons (Fig. 2).

For the 2015–2025 period, we used the HAB_f INDEX to characterize the distribution and risk of HAB events. Since the algorithm includes all harmful species in its calculation, it is particularly useful for general analyses

of HAB dynamics. Overall results from POAS+ (Figs. 3, 5) show no significant increase in the frequency or intensity of the HAB_f INDEX over the past decade. However, the frequency of HAB events varies among species [11]. For example, *A. catenella* was less frequent during the past 10 years, while *P. micans*, *H.*

akashiwo, and *Pseudochattonella* were more frequent during the same period.

HAB events in SCMI are driven by multiple factors. Climate anomalies, for instance, can alter freshwater inflows and lead to oceanographic changes, such as shifts in nutrient stoichiometry [12] in estuaries and fjords, creating favourable niches for certain species. Some photoautotrophic flagellates are better adapted to these changing nutrient ratios (less silicate) and to density gradients. On a broader scale, global phenomena such as El Niño can create environmental conditions that favour HAB development, as observed in 2016, among others.

Looking ahead, our main challenge is to automate the monitoring programme using *in situ* digital and bio-imaging technologies, combining them with predictive numerical models or machine learning algorithms. This approach could enable a more robust and responsive monitoring system—one capable of reducing or mitigating the negative effects of HABs.

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Striving for a sustainable surveillance of Ciguatera Poisoning in the Pacific: the Ciguawatch initiative

The South Pacific region is a well known historical hotspot for Ciguatera Poisoning (CP) [1], with the first poisoning incidents reported from Vanuatu dating back to the early 17th century. According to Skinner et al. [2], taking into account under-reporting, an estimated 500,000 Pacific islanders might have suffered from CP between 1973 and 2008, with a 60% increase in incidence rates between 1973–1983 and 1998–2008. Such statistics highlight the major threat CP poses in terms of social equity for Pacific Island Countries and Territories (PICTs), communities for whom fish products represent not only a subsistence resource but also a significant source of income [3, 4]. Besides its widely recognized health and socioeconomic impacts, CP also has strong cultural ramifications often overlooked: in some cases, the fear of CP can lead to

a permanent dietary shift among local populations, and even to a disruption in the transmission of traditional subsistence fishing knowledge between generations [3]. In this context, benefiting from effective CP risk monitoring and prevention programs is critical for these communities.

Successful CP risk surveillance depends on the availability of accurate epidemiological data [5], in conjunction with the implementation of environmental monitoring programs. Yet, to date, most PICTs already confronted with CP outbreaks still lack official statistics due to the absence of proper reporting systems, while others not yet affected by this disease are seeking to prepare to face this emerging risk, especially in light of the effects of global change. In this regard, French Polynesia (FP) stands as an exception, as it is one of the few nations having a

research unit devoted to the study of CP since the early 1960s, and an ongoing monitoring program since 2007 [6].

The expertise developed by the Laboratory of Marine Biotoxins of the Louis Malardé Institute (ILM) over the past two decades has led to the development of innovative IT tools, e.g. the dedicated CP websites [7, 8] which provide (i) a wide range of downloadable information on CP, and (ii) allow data collection and access to CP interactive maps, and statistics on CP epidemiology including a list of CP-prone fish species in FP islands. Building on these assets, the Pacific Ciguawatch initiative led by ILM, was launched in 2022 to promote/facilitate the deployment of tailored risk assessment and management programmes in PICTs showing an interest in implementing local CP mitigation strategies.

This initiative relies mainly on the use of the training and CP data sharing e-platform [8], which provides SOPs, video tutorials, technical guides, educational brochures, etc., relating to the sampling and report of the causative microalgae's geographic distribution and biodiversity, as well as improved CP case diagnosis and data collection. A specific module dedicated to the development of tailored community awareness material targeted at the general public, fishers and healthcare worker occupational groups has also been made available.

In 2022–2024, Fiji, Samoa, and Tonga, which have identified CP as a national priority in terms of sea-food safety, food security and nutrition, were trained using the Ciguawatch tools in the frame of the FAO-SAP Technical Cooperation Programme TCP/SAP/3807.

Wallis and Futuna (WF) has had an existing national CP surveillance program since 2015, which helped confirm the presence of *Gambierdiscus* spp. in WF waters, and Futuna as a CP hotspot (85 % of the 122 cases reported between 2018–2024 originated from Futuna). In light of the recent increase in CP incidents in Futuna, local authorities expressed the need to strengthen the country's monitoring and management capacities. In response, a sectorial agreement was signed between the Territory of WF and French Polynesia in November 2023, on the sidelines of the

Fig. 1. Audience of members of the scientific team with her Majesty Lavelua of Wallis (extreme right).

Fig. 2. Location of the eight sampling sites around the islands of (A) Wallis and (B) Futuna.

Fig. 3. Training to the deployment and collection of window screen devices.

52nd Pacific Islands Forum. Hence, from February to September 2024, remote online training sessions were delivered to several Environment, Fisheries, and Health stakeholders. The present article describes the field activities conducted from April 19th to May 5th, 2025 in WF, as a follow-up to this online training.

In many PICTs where customs and traditions are an important part of everyday life, scientific missions involving field activities must receive

the approval of the local king or moral authorities. Hence, no sampling activities could be carried out before an audience with her Majesty Lavelua Patalione Takumasiva Aisake of Wallis, and the two customary chiefs of Sigave and Alo in Futuna (Fig. 1).

In the field, the technical team of the Environment Department of WF was trained in the environmental surveillance of CP through the deployment and collection of window

screen devices over a total of eight sites in WF (Figs. 2–3) using the artificial substrate method described by Tester et al. [9]. These sites were selected based on previous dinoflagellate surveillance data and reports of CP cases collated by the Environment and Health departments. Back at the laboratory, samples were processed and analyzed by microscope observations under the supervision of ILM team (Fig. 4: A,B).

In parallel, several information interventions targeted at healthcare professionals of Sia (Wallis) and Kaleveleve (Futuna) hospitals were conducted in order to improve CP base knowledge, diagnosis and case reporting using a dedicated application via the Ciguawatch platform [10]. In light of the high turnover of the medical staff, all information supports were made available to local health authorities for systematic dissemination to newly arrived staff members. Although CP reporting is not mandatory in WF, the objective of this communication strategy was to alert stakeholders to the importance of accurate CP reporting to support further customized prevention actions. Most importantly, the use of standardized data collection methodologies is meant to ultimately facilitate the comparison of CP status and trends across PICTs.

Finally, younger audiences were not left out, with an educational intervention conducted with two classes of the Malae'fo'ou Elementary School actively involved in a Marine Education Area programme (Fig. 5).

As of now, Health agents can start feeding epidemiological data

Fig. 4. (A) Window screen sample processing and (B) microscope observations for microalgae identification training session.

Fig. 5. (A) School-based intervention in the Elementary school of Mala'efo'ou (Wallis); (B) example of infographic supports used to illustrate CP to a young audience.

onto the Ciguawatch platform. Additionally, window screen samples and fish specimens will be collected by Environment staff, and sent to ILM to characterize *Gambierdiscus* spp. diversity in WF waters by qPCR and for toxicity analyses, respectively. Future activities stipulated in the sectoral agreement signed between WF and FP also include the training of Environment agents in various extraction techniques, as well as internships for WF students at ILM.

The momentum initiated through this regional cooperation programme will hopefully contribute to establish a good inter-agency dynamics and communication, which in turn will benefit the effective surveillance and management of CP incidents in WF.

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Mireille Chinain, recipient of the ISSHA Yasumoto Award, poses with her present (Gambierdiscus carving from Prof Takayama) after the 20th ICHA held in Hiroshima. October 2023.

Unusual co-occurrence of *Prorocentrum lima* and *P. rhathymum* in a mucilaginous river plume in a tropical Atlantic estuary (northeast Brazil)

Prorocentrum is a morphologically distinctive genus of desmokyont dinoflagellates found in both planktonic and benthic environments. This genus has a broad geographic distribution and play an important role in marine trophic dynamics [1–2]. Epiphytic species of *Prorocentrum* are frequently found in shallow tropical waters, attached to substrates such as macroalgae, coral reefs, and sediments by producing mucous polysaccharide filaments [3]. Despite their benthic distribution, these species have flagella and can get detached, transitioning into a planktonic form during part of their vegetative cycle [4]. Warm water temperatures typically enhance their growth and distribution, especially in tropical regions [4], where the response of biological communities to increasing temperature remains an open question with high relevance in global climate change projections [5].

In recent decades, there has been a considerable numerical increase in reports about the intensification of toxic or harmful algal blooms (HABs), with implications for ecological balance and human health [6]. Although HABs are most commonly associated with planktonic species, benthic species may

cause Benthic Harmful Algal Blooms (BHABs) [7]. These noxious blooms occur when toxigenic dinoflagellates are transferred through the food web, leading to shellfish poisoning events that affect marine fauna (including vertebrates) and humans. In addition, some species may reach high cell densities and release toxins in the seawater and the atmosphere, which can cause skin irritation and breathing difficulties in sunbathers. Among the toxigenic benthic dinoflagellates, *Prorocentrum lima* and *Prorocentrum rhathymum* are well-known species of concern. *P. lima* has been linked to diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP) outbreaks in several regions [8], while *P. rhathymum*, a tycho planktonic species previously identified as *P. mexicanum*, has been associated with red tide (discolouration) events in tropical systems [9]. On tropical and subtropical Atlantic coasts, both species have been documented as contributors to toxin-related events. In Brazilian waters, *P. lima* has been reported from latitudes 8°S to 27°S, consistently appearing attached to macroalgae [7], but most studies have focused on cultures or epiphyte collections, with limited understanding of the ecology

and behaviour of field populations.

During a field survey on 3 September 2021, a yellow-brownish foam with a greasy appearance was observed in a river plume at the upstream section of the Serinhaém River, within Camamu Bay, Bahia, Brazil (13°43'38.8"S; 39°08'04.0"W) (Fig. 1). This plume measured approximately eight meters long and one meter wide (Fig. 2). This estuarine region, surrounded by protected mangrove and Atlantic Forest vegetation ("mata Atlântica"), supports artisanal fisheries and tourism. A sample of the foam was manually collected in a plastic container without preservatives and immediately cooled for transport. Environmental variables including temperature, pH, depth, and salinity were recorded in situ using standard multiparameter probes and equipment. Water transparency was measured using a Secchi disk. Samples for nutrient analysis were cooled and frozen for spectrophotometric analysis following established protocols [10]. Light microscopic observation of the foam aggregates revealed a mixture of several *Prorocentrum* species (Fig. 3). Cell counts were estimated according to the Utermöhl method, with 2 mL of homogenized sample analyzed under an inverted microscope at 400× magnification. Thirty random transects were examined and extrapolated to estimate total concentrations. The estimated cell concentrations were 2.04×10^6 cells·L⁻¹ for *P. rhathymum* and 1.69×10^6 cells·L⁻¹ for the *P. lima* complex. Cells were well preserved, with visible chloroplasts,

Fig. 1. (A) Geographic location of the Serinhaém River estuary in the State of Bahia, Brazil (X indicates the site where the bloom was observed). (B) Zoomed view showing the urban occupation of Ituberá along the river margins near the sampling site.

Fig. 2. A) Field photograph of the surface foam plume observed on 3 September 2021; B) Close-up photograph of the foam, highlighting its greasy, yellow-brownish mucilaginous texture.

starch sheaths, mucocysts, and pyrenoids. Some empty thecae were observed. Taxonomic identification was confirmed using scanning electron microscopy after dehydration and critical point drying. Morphological criteria for species identification included periflagellar platelets, anterior spines, trichocyst pore arrangements, and overall dimensions [2]. *P. rathymum* displayed reticulated-foveate surface ornamentation and pore lines radiating from a central point. Cells were elliptical or oblong, with plates measuring 36–42 μm in length and 24–30 μm in width,

with a length-to-width ratio of approximately 1.4. The *P. lima* complex exhibited kidney-shaped pores and a smaller length-to-width ratio (1.25–2.35), with plate sizes of 36–42 μm in length and 17–33 μm in width. Images showed multiple cells aggregated and embedded in mucilage, possibly indicating in situ aggregation. Light microscopy further revealed chloroplasts and starch rings in both species (Fig. 4).

At the time of sampling, the water temperature was 25.3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, salinity 15.6, pH 6.58, and river depth was 11.6 m. The concentrations of total phosphorus,

total nitrogen, and phosphate were 1.30 $\mu\text{M}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, 19.6 $\mu\text{M}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, and 0.3 $\mu\text{M}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, respectively. These nutrient levels suggest nitrogen enrichment and phosphorus limitation—conditions often associated with eutrophication and anthropogenic impact in estuarine environments [6–7]. The estimated N:P ratio at the bloom site exceeded 100:1, a significant indicator of potential ecological imbalance. Similar high N:P ratios have been in other systems have been interpreted as signs of phosphorus limitation, especially in the freshwater sections of estuaries where nitrogen

Fig. 3. Light micrograph (10 \times magnification) of the collected foam sample, illustrating the dense particulate (right) and cellular matter (left) and a zoomed view of an aggregation of *Prorocentrum lima* complex and *Prorocentrum rathymum* cells within the sample debris.

Fig. 4. Scanning electron micrograph showing dinoflagellate specimens aggregated onto a macroalgal debris fragment (left) and light micrograph displaying *P. lima* complex and *P. rathymum* side-by-side within the fixed sample slide, with visible features such as chloroplasts, nuclei, anterior spine, periflagellar platelets, starch ring, and trichocysts (right).

often dominates [6]. The measured environmental conditions—nutrient availability, light penetration, and reduced turbulence—are conducive to HAB formation [6]. Tropical temperatures may further favour *Prorocentrum* proliferation [4], while low turbulence in upstream estuarine zones may facilitate mucilaginous aggregations that appear as surface foam.

The bloom occurred adjacent to urban areas with low levels of sewage treatment—only 36% of domestic waste is treated in Ituberá—suggesting anthropogenic nutrient input [11]. While causality cannot be firmly established, the Brazilian demographic census reported 4.6 diarrhoea-related hospital admissions per 1,000 residents in this region, which is consistent with DSP symptomatology [7].

A broader environmental characterization of the Serinhaém River estuary, including areas without such foam plumes, is provided by Noga et al (2025) [11]. That study offer additional insight into the estuary's hydrology, nutrient gradients, anthropogenic pressures, and spatial heterogeneity relevant to interpreting the bloom described herein. To the best of our knowledge, this bloom is the first of its kind recorded in Atlantic waters. Only one other bloom of *P. rathymum* with similar characteristics has been reported—in the Bangaram lagoon,

India—where similar yellow-brownish mucilaginous foams were observed [9]. The resemblance in colour, texture, and species composition suggests that such blooms may occur in other tropical systems under similar environmental conditions. This event is of particular concern given the local reliance on fish and shellfish for subsistence and commerce. The presence of high concentrations of *P. lima* and *P. rathymum*—two toxigenic species—highlights the need for monitoring, particularly in regions lacking HAB surveillance. The co-occurrence of these species in a free-floating, bloom-forming state is unprecedented in this region and contributes to our understanding of their ecological plasticity. Their ability to shift to a planktonic state, especially in eutrophic tropical estuaries, expands the risk they pose to ecosystem health and human populations. With ongoing coastal urbanization and rising temperatures, such events may become more frequent.

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Will 2025 witness another extensive mucilage outbreak in the Marmara Sea?

For people living around the Marmara Sea, which connects the Mediterranean Sea to the Black Sea (spanning 40°30'0" N to 41°00'00" N, 26°41'60" E to 30°00'00" E), spring 2021 was unusual due to a widespread mucilage event (Fig. 1a). Marine mucilage, also called sea snot, is composed of mucous aggregates exuded by some phytoplankton species, particularly the dinoflagellate *Gonyaulax fragilis* [1]. Mucilage presence was initially reported in the water column in the Dardanelles Strait (west of the Marmara Sea, Fig. 1a) from December 2020 to March 2021 [2]. Large surface aggregations were

also observed at this location in satellite imagery, starting in March 2021 (Fig. 1c), and later developed into a massive outbreak impacting the entire Marmara Sea (Fig. 1a). Satellite observations show peak mucilage abundance around 4 May 2021 (displayed in Fig. 1a; [3]), with the event ending in June.

The 2021 mucilage outbreak directly harmed the economy of Turkey (officially "Türkiye") due to travel cancellations impacting the tourism sector, which plays an important role in Turkey's GDP [4]. It also impacted fisheries [5], likely by causing enormous environmental damage such as oxidative

stress to seafood [6], or leading to mass mortality of benthic species [7] due to suffocation from mucilage (Fig. 2). Fish (particularly juveniles) also faced direct mass mortality resulting from the mucilage, with more than 10,000 individuals found dead over only four stations in the south of the Marmara Sea [8]. Although mucilage events also previously occurred in the Marmara Sea, notably in October 2007 and 2008, as well as in the adjacent Adriatic Sea ([9], submitted), the 2021 event represented a temporal (presence across ~three months) and a spatial (covered almost the entire region) record for the Marmara Sea [3].

For the current bloom, mucilage presence inside the water column was reported in December 2024 in the Dardanelles Strait (Fig. 3) and surface features were visible using satellite

Fig. 1. (a) MODIS-Aqua False-Red-Blue-Green (FRGB) image collected on 4 May 2021 showing presence of mucilage (white-yellow mesoscale slicks) across the entire Marmara Sea. (b) Inset highlighting the location of the Marmara Sea, between the Aegean Sea and Black Sea. (c) Sentinel-2 FRGB image collected on 28 March 2021 in the Dardanelles Strait (west of the Marmara Sea) showing surface aggregations of mucilage, two months before the outbreak displayed in (a). (d) Sentinel-2 FRGB image collected on 21 April 2025 in the Dardanelles Strait showing similar surface mucilage aggregations as panel (c).

Fig. 2. Mucilage covering the sea floor in the Aegean Sea, west of the Dardanelles Strait (near the city of Gökçeada, Turkey, 40°12'00" N, 25°53'60" E)], in February 2025. Images from <https://www.turkeyrecap.com/p/dawn-of-the-dead-zone-winter-mucilage>.

data covering the Strait in April 2025 (Fig. 1c). The reflectance spectral shapes of these features suggest that they are also caused by mucilage. Additional satellite data collected on 21 April 2025 (the same date as Fig. 1d) also show small mucilage features in the southeast of the Marmara Sea, near the city of Gemlik (Turkey, displayed on Fig. 1a). Do these observations precede another massive mucilage outbreak in the Marmara Sea in May–June 2025, similar to what happened in 2021? Will the delay in timing of the first surface aggregations (March in 2021, compared to April in 2025) also delay the potential outbreak to June – July, and might the environmental impacts (e.g., to juvenile fish populations) also differ as a result?

The specific conditions that cause *Gonyaulax fragilis*, or other potential mucilage producing species, to exudate large amounts of mucilage are unknown. Warmer temperatures in the region are believed to favor mucilage production [10], but additional factors may be required to precondition an outbreak. Indeed, relevant conditions leading to the mucilage outbreak in the northern Adriatic Sea during summer 2024 included elevated wintertime temperature, stratification, and subsequent nutrient influx from river discharge [11]. Whether or not the current mucilage presence is a harbinger of an eventual Marmara-wide outbreak during late Spring 2025 (mirroring the 2021 progression), this developing natural experiment offers the opportunity to monitor the event and collect key environmental

Fig. 3. In water mucilage aggregation in the Dardanelles Strait, picturing a diver surrounded by mucilage in December 2024. Image from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=akmwjqk96k4>.

variables. Such efforts may improve understanding of this phenomenon toward potential mitigation and remediation efforts.

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HARMFUL Phytoplankton Species in the Central Colombian Caribbean Oceanic Province

Fig. 1. Sampling sites in the Colombian Central Caribbean Oceanic Province.

Historically, research on phytoplankton and phytobenthos from the Colombian Caribbean Sea has focused on neritic waters. This neritic zone, constitutes less than 6% (30,219 km²) of the total Colombian Caribbean area, whereas the remaining 94% (501,935 km²) remains largely unexplored. A review of the extant literature revealed the presence of 13 harmful microalgal species in coastal waters of the Colombian Caribbean (Table 1).

To ascertain the presence and distribution of harmful microalgae in the oceanic waters of the Colombian Caribbean, the IOC-UNESCO taxonomic reference list of harmful microalgae [1] was used to verify the species reported in a recent investigation, which analysed the phytoplankton composition in 108 samples collected during three expeditions to the Central Colombian Caribbean Oceanic Province (CCOP) [2].

Oceanographic expeditions were conducted during 2015, 2016, and 2017, encompassing a total area of 35,874 km² and 27 stations situated in the vicinity of the Magdalena River, a major waterway in the country (Fig. 1). Water samples were collected using Niskin bottles at 10, 80, and 250 m; vertical tows covering the upper 50 m were conducted using nets with a 20-µm mesh size.

Bottle samples were analysed using the Utermöhl method, and net samples were examined from aliquots (0.125 ml) using accumulation curves. Cells were observed using a Leica Microsystems DMi1 inverted microscope using 20×, 40×, and 63× objectives. Identification was performed to the lowest possible taxonomic level, following various taxonomic keys [3–5]. Using this method, 287 taxa were recorded, and 184 species were identified. A subsequent comparison of taxonomic lists revealed that only 14 species in the CCOP list are considered harmful, of which six are deemed potentially toxic (Table 2). These organisms were identified in the epipelagic zone of the Caribbean Surface Water (CSW), encompassing the upper 10 m, with average temperatures of 28 °C, salinity 36, and dissolved oxygen concentrations of 3.8 mg L⁻¹.

The presence of potentially toxic species such as *Karenia papilionacea* and *Prorocentrum concavum* was also

Table 1. Harmful microalgae species reported in coastal waters of the Colombian Caribbean coast [6–7].

Species	Associated Toxins
<i>Prorocentrum borbonicum</i> L.Ten-Hage, J.Turquet, J.-P.Quod, S.Puiseux-Dao & Couté 2000	Neurotoxic borbotoxins
<i>Prorocentrum cordatum</i> (Ostenfeld) J.D.Dodge 1976	Fast Acting Toxins
<i>Prorocentrum hoffmannianum</i> M.A.Faust 1990	Okadaic acid, Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins, Fast Acting Toxins
<i>Prorocentrum lima</i> (Ehrenberg) F.Stein 1878	Okadaic acid, DTX-1, DTX-2, prorocontrolide, Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxin, Fast Acting Toxins
<i>Prorocentrum porosum</i> Arteaga-Sogamoso, F.Rodríguez, Amato, Ben-Gigirey, Tibiriçá, Chomerat, Mafra, T.Nishimura, M.Adachi & Mancera-Pineda 2022	Okadaic acid
<i>Prorocentrum rhathymum</i> A.R.Loeblich III, Sherley & R.J.Schmidt 1979	Okadaic acid
<i>Gonyaulax</i> sp. Diesing, 1866	Yessotoxins
<i>Gambierdiscus caribaeus</i> Vandersea, Litaker, M.A.Faust, Kibler, W.C.Holland & P.A.Tester 2009	CTX, IC-CTX analogue, 44-methylgambierone, positive to the Human erythrocyte lysis assay
<i>Ostreopsis cf. ovata</i> Y.Fukuyo 1981	Ovatoxins
<i>Margalefidinium polykrikoides</i> (Margalef) F.Gómez, Richlen & D.M.Anderson 2017	
<i>Anabaena spiroides f. baltica</i> (Johs.Schmidt) Pankow 1965	
<i>Anabaenopsis</i> sp. V.V.Miller, 1923	
<i>Synechocystis</i> sp. Sauvageau, 1892	

Table 2. Harmful microalgae found in the Colombian Central Caribbean Oceanic Province – CCOP.

Type	Species name	Environment and Associated Toxins
Toxic Species	<i>Centrodinium punctatum</i> (Cleve) E.J.R.Taylor 1976	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Saxitoxins, Paralytic Shellfish Toxins
	<i>Dinophysis caudata</i> Kent 1881	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Okadaic acid, DTX1, Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins
	<i>Dinophysis ovum</i> F.Schütt 1895	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Okadaic acid, Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins
	<i>Karenia papilionacea</i> A.J.Haywood & K.A.Steidinger 2004	Subtropical Subsurface Water – Epipelagic Zone Brevetoxins
	<i>Phalacroma mitra</i> F.Schütt 1895	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins
	<i>Prorocentrum concavum</i> Y.Fukuyo 1981	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Subtropical Subsurface Water – Epipelagic Zone Okadaic acid, DTX1, Fast Acting Toxins
Harmful non-toxic	<i>Prorocentrum dentatum</i> F.Stein 1883	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Subtropical Subsurface Water – Epipelagic Zone
	<i>Prorocentrum micans</i> Ehrenberg 1834	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone
	<i>Tripes dens</i> (Ostenfeld & Johannes Schmidt) F.Gómez 2013	
	<i>Tripes furca</i> (Ehrenberg) F.Gómez 2013	
	<i>Tripes karstenii</i> (Pavillard) F.Gómez 2021	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Subtropical Subsurface Water – Epipelagic Zone
	<i>Tripes muelleri</i> Bory 1826	
	<i>Tripes fusus</i> (Ehrenberg) F.Gómez 2013	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Subtropical Subsurface Water – Epipelagic Zone
<i>Cerataulina pelagica</i> (Cleve) Hendeby 1937	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Subtropical Subsurface Water – Epipelagic Zone Subtropical Subsurface Water – Mesopelagic Zone	

confirmed in Subtropical Subsurface Waters (SSW), characterized by average temperatures of 21 °C, a salinity of 36, and dissolved oxygen concentrations of around 3 mg·L⁻¹. Among the 15 compounds classified as toxic substances identified in the IOC-UNESCO list for the six species in question, the most prevalent were okadaic acid and the diarrhetic toxins (Table 2).

Non-toxic harmful species, such as *Prorocentrum dentatum*, *Tripes fusus*,

and *Cerataulina pelagica*, were also identified in the epipelagic zone of the SSW. The latter species was also observed in the mesopelagic zone of the SSW, at depths close to 250 m.

The CCOP is an industrial fishing zone of significant importance to the nation's economy and food security. The focus in this zone is on the capture of pelagic species, including *Coryphaena hippurus*, *Thunnus* spp., and *Makaira* spp. Therefore, the presence of these

HAB species highlights the need to implement a monitoring programme for marine toxins. Such a programme would help prevent potential public health problems and mitigate risks to the fishing and tourism industries.

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High-vertical resolution sampling reveals sharp Thin Layers of Toxic Phytoplankton in the Patagonian Fjords, Southern Chile

Fig. 1. Map of the study area showing: (A) Northern Chilean Patagonia inland sea (the black box delimits the Puyuhuapi fjord), and (B) The study area and sampling stations (red circles) in Puyuhuapi fjord.

Thin layers of phytoplankton (TLP) are narrow (a few cm to less than 5m) bands of water where aggregated cells and their pigments may reach biomass levels (chlorophyll *a*, cell densities) several orders of magnitude higher than the layers immediately above or below [1]. These layers are the result of complex interactions between physical (vertical gradients in density and water velocity) and biological (swimming, buoyancy control, behaviour) processes and are ecologically significant. TLPs act as microenvironments where biological activity is enhanced, influencing processes such as primary productivity, trophic web transfers and the accumulation of bioactive compounds—including both particulate and dissolved shellfish toxins [2].

Thin Layers of toxin-producing microalgae may also act as a “toxic carpet”, posing a significant threat to caged-fish and to bivalves cultivated on long lines and suspended rafts [3]. TLPs often arise from a “stretched” subsurface chlorophyll maximum and may go undetected when only conventional bottle sampling at fixed

depth intervals—or worse, only surface waters collected with a bucket—are collected in the framework of HAB monitoring programmes [4]. Here, we describe TLPs formed by two lipophilic toxin producers, *Dinophysis acuminata* and *Dinophysis acuta*, and their associated toxins in the southern Chilean fjords. These *Dinophysis* species are known to produce two kinds of toxins: Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins (DST: okadaic acid, OA, and Dinophysistoxins, DTXs) and Pectenotoxins (PTXs) [5]. The diarrhetic toxins are bioaccumulated by mussels and other filter feeders, which act as vectors, transferring them through the food web. Consumers of contaminated shellfish may suffer from the diarrhetic shellfish poisoning syndrome. To protect public health, shellfish harvesting is prohibited whenever toxin levels in the shellfish meat exceed regulatory thresholds, leading to significant economic losses for the shellfish industry. Furthermore, harmful effects of both DSTs and PTXs—whether particulate or dissolved—on larval stages of molluscs, crustaceans and fish, have been demonstrated

under laboratory conditions. However, their impact on the recruitment of commercially important species in the wild remains poorly understood [6-7].

The Patagonian fjords, characterised by permanent strong salinity gradients, high water residence times, and estuarine-like circulation patterns, provide optimal conditions for the formation and persistence of TLPs [8]. Describing the physical and chemical characteristics of these microstructures is crucial for understanding the optimal species (strain)-specific conditions that favour growth and toxin production. This knowledge is key to enhancing early warning systems and predictive models.

In 23 November 2023, a survey was carried out in Puyuhuapi fjord (Fig. 1A), off Puerto Cisnes (Fig. 1B) to compare vertical profiles of *Dinophysis* species obtained through conventional methods (Niskin bottles sampled every 2 m) with those from a high vertical resolution sampler (MAR = muestreador de alta resolución) (Fig. 2). This sampling device, made in Chile, was inspired by the Fine-Scale Sampler

(FSS) developed at Ifremer [9]. The Chilean MAR, adapted to sample the narrow mixed layer (around 10m) and sharp haloclines in the fjords, consists of a 2 m high by 38.5 cm wide rectangular frame, fitted with eight 1.7 L Niskin bottles spaced 25 cm apart. CTD (Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth) casts from the surface to 20 m depth were used to determine, in real time, the vertical distribution of temperature, salinity, and *in vivo* *Chl a* fluorescence (F)—key parameters for tracking the position and characteristics (depth, width, intensity) of the TLP. The CTD data were processed and visualized using RStudio software.

For the quantitative analysis of *Dinophysis* species, 100ml aliquots from each conventional bottle (0–20 m every 4m) and MAR sample, were transferred to UV-protected, screw-cap glass jars and immediately fixed with Lugol's

solution. Between 10 and 25 mL of each fixed sample were allowed to sediment overnight in Utermöhl chambers, and large *Dinophysis* cells were counted using an Olympus CX40 inverted microscope at 100× magnification (detection limit: 40–100 cells·L⁻¹).

For analysis of lipophilic toxins, 1 L aliquots from each bottle were filtered through Whatman GF/F fibreglass filters (47 mm, 0,7 µm pore size). The filters were stored in cryotubes and sent to the analytical chemistry laboratory for lipophilic toxin analysis, following protocols described in [10].

Throughout the sampling campaign, the fjord exhibited a strong haline stratification in the top 5 m (Fig. 3A). Water temperature ranged from 11 to 10 °C, with a minimum of 9 °C at 1–2 m depth. A pronounced salinity gradient (5 to 25 PSU) was observed between 5 and 15 m—typical mid-spring conditions in

Puyuhuapi Fjord, attributed to heavy freshwater discharge from the Cisnes River following snowmelt [11]. The CTD fluorescence sensor detected a sharp chlorophyll fluorescence maximum equivalent to 46.6 µg·L⁻¹ *Chl a* at a depth of 4.8 m (Fig. 3A), meeting the criteria proposed by Dekshenieks et al. [1] for defining a thin layer.

Marked differences were observed between the cell density profiles derived from conventional and MAR sampling (Fig. 3B). Conventional methods detected a maximum density of *D. acuminata* of 4,000 cells·L⁻¹ at 4 m—coinciding with peaks in OA (1.9 ng·mL⁻¹) and PTX2 (14.4 ng·mL⁻¹)—and a *D. acuta* cell maximum (200 cells·L⁻¹) at 6 m, i.e., 2 m above the DTX1 maximum (0,1 ng·mL⁻¹) (Fig. 3B). In contrast, MEF sampling revealed a five-fold higher *D. acuminata* density (20,800 cells·L⁻¹) at 4 m, with correspondingly higher OA (4.7 ng·mL⁻¹), DTX1 (0.1 ng·mL⁻¹), and PTX2 (25 ng·mL⁻¹) concentrations (Fig. 3C). A shift in toxin distribution was also detected, with the toxin peak at 4.5 m coinciding with a *D. acuta* maximum of 900 cells·L⁻¹. The results presented here show that the MAR provides enhanced resolution for detecting the vertical distribution of *Dinophysis* species and their associated toxins. It also enables a more accurate estimation of the real magnitude of the toxic dinoflagellate population—critical for estimating division rates and other key ecological parameters. In summary, high-vertical resolution sampling yields more realistic information on the spatial distribution and physiological status of target species. Such strategies are particularly important in strongly stratified systems like the Chilean fjords, which host both valuable aquaculture operations and protected nature reserves and are increasingly exposed to various harmful algal bloom events—including shellfish toxin producers, fish-killing species, and high-biomass nuisance blooms [6].

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Fig. 2. Fine scale sampler (Mar = Muestreador de Alta Resolución) a sampling device with a vertical resolution of 25 cm. (A) A fin providing stability to the structure submerged in the water, (B) Skeleton of the structure where the (C) Eight Niskin bottles of 1.7 L are positioned.

Fig. 3. (A) Vertical profiles of temperature, salinity, and chlorophyll concentration. The gray-shaded area indicates the range where samples were collected using the MAR (3–5 m). (B) Vertical distribution of *Dinophysis acuta* and *Dinophysis acuminata* (0–20 meters) along with the vertical distribution of their associated lipophilic toxins. The gray-shaded area indicates the MAR sampling depth interval (3–5 m). (C) High-resolution vertical distribution of *Dinophysis* species and their lipophilic toxins between 3–5 meters.

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Fig. 4. Preparing the high vertical resolution profiler before sampling. Puyuhuapi Fjord, Aysén, Chile, 2025.

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The International Training Program on Prevention, Control, and Mitigation of Harmful Algal Blooms: bridging HAB control requirements with the latest, effective and applicable technologies

Harmful algal blooms (HABs) are ecological disasters that affects the sustainability of ecosystems and pose serious threats to mariculture industries and human health worldwide. Significant efforts have been directed towards the Prevention, Control, and Mitigation (PCM) of HABs. A variety of technologies and approaches have been developed and implemented, including rapid species detection methods using molecular techniques (e.g., qPCR, genetic chips), the Environmental Sample Processor (ESP), and the Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB). Additionally, clay dispersal has been introduced and demonstrated as an effective solution for mitigating HABs, having been extensively applied in China and Korea for decades. Nonetheless, a dedicated training programme that bridges stakeholder needs and available resources has yet to be established. A considerable gap remains between stakeholders seeking to decrease HAB impacts and the current advancements in PCMHAB research, highlighting the urgent

need for enhanced collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Endorsed by SCOR-IOC GlobalHAB, the first training program on PCMHAB, organized by the Institute of Oceanology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (IOCAS), in partnership with Guangxi Academy of Sciences, Qingdao Marine Science and Technology Center, and local authorities of Guangxi Province, was held in Nanning and Fangchenggang, Guangxi, China from 1 to 11 December 2024. This initiative employed China's advanced technology and practical expertise in HAB control, specifically Modified Clay (MC), to provide professional training in this field. It also features lectures and discussions on cutting-edge technologies related to PCM, including HAB monitoring and early warning systems, thereby contributing to global efforts in PCMHABs. More than 50 trainees from 15 nations participated, while experts from GlobalHAB, the PICES HAB group, and the IOC-WEST-PAC HAB group contributed either in person or virtually. The total number of participants, including experts, train-

ees, Early Career Ocean Professionals (ECOP) from both international and local Chinese institutions, approached 200 (Fig. 1A).

During the event, representatives from participating countries endorsed the "Controlling Global Coastal Harmful Algal Blooms (HAB-C)" initiative through the signing of a Memorandum of Understanding (Fig. 1B). Signatories—including the United States, Peru, and the Guangxi Academy of Sciences—agreed to explore internationally coordinated strategies for HAB management, aiming to enhance collaboration in safeguarding marine ecological health through scientific research and practical applications.

The main activities of this program included lectures, laboratory exercises, and fieldwork. Lectures addressed the occurrence of HABs in various countries, the identification of causative organisms, early warning and monitoring systems, algal toxin detection, and economic impacts. A strong emphasis was placed on MC technology through theoretical studies,

Fig. 1. (A) Group photo. (B) Signing ceremony. (C) Lecture series by experts.

Fig. 2. Laboratory sessions.

safety assessments, and expert-led sessions (Fig. 1C).

During laboratory practices, trainees practiced microscopy-based identification and qPCR detection of HAB species and participated in hands-on experiments using MC. These activities included evaluating cell removal efficiency by MC and assessing its impact and safety on aquaculture organisms (Fig. 2). Fieldwork took place along the Fangchenggang coast, where trainees progressively acquired skills in MC sprayer assembly, mixing, and application. Under expert guidance, they simulated a HAB event and successfully applied MC-based mitigation strategies

(Fig. 3A). In addition to the training activities, cultural components were incorporated into the programme. Trainees visited the Guangxi Museum of Nationalities to gain an appreciation of Chinese traditional culture (Fig. 3B). Additionally, they visited local aquaculture farms and engaged with technical personnel to learn about fish and shrimp farming practices powered by solar energy.

The successful and efficient execution of the International Training Programme on PCM-HAB has established a valuable platform for exchange and collaboration, connecting stakeholder needs with the latest

technologies. It has laid the groundwork for the HAB-C Project and promoted the dissemination and adoption of relevant knowledge and practices. This initiative is expected to provide robust support for the future protection of global marine ecosystems and the effective prevention and control of HABs, contributing to the sustainability of our shared blue planet.

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Fig. 3. Field practices (A) and cultural visits (B).

New Programme: Changing Microalgal Communities

Changing Microalgal Communities is a five-year collaborative research programme funded by the New Zealand government and led by the Cawthron Institute in Nelson. Launched in October 2024, the programme aims to enhance our understanding of microalgal communities in New Zealand's coastal waters, investigate the drivers of change within these ecosystems, and assess the cascading effects on marine environments.

The programme's outcomes will include improved monitoring, forecasting, and communication strategies for microalgae and harmful algal blooms (HABs), supported by novel, fit-for-purpose tools. While the programme has a strong focus on HABs, it also examines how climate change is affecting beneficial microalgal communities. This knowledge will underpin effective mitigation and restoration approaches that can be used by management agencies, coastal communities, and industry to protect our marine ecosystems, safeguard

public health, and enable sustainable development of the blue economy.

Inaugural Wānanga: A Collaborative Start

In February 2025, the programme's first face-to-face wānanga (Māori: discussion or workshop) took place over two days in Nelson. This gathering brought together a diverse team of experts from Māori organisations, local councils, research institutes and industry partners from across the country. The event fostered collaboration and strengthened relationships among participants, setting the foundation for the research ahead.

A key focus of this meeting was to evaluate current tools and methodologies for sampling coastal microalgal communities at several case study sites across the country. Discussions centred on refining holistic monitoring protocols that will be implemented throughout the programme. Leads from each case

study site provided valuable insights into regional challenges and unique ecological conditions. Participants also explored various sampling tool options and planned the locations of sampling sites for the coming years. The group also engaged in discussions to develop the tikanga (Māori: protocols) for the programme for sampling, sample handling, and data governance, ensuring the establishment of culturally and scientifically sound research practices for the programme.

The insights and collaborations from this wānanga have laid a solid basis for the next stages of the programme, as we work together to be proactive in the prediction and managing changes in microalgal community changes in New Zealand.

For more information, please contact CMC programme leads: Anne Rolton Vignier or Kirsty Smith, email: cmc@cawthron.org.nz.

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Fig. 1. Clockwise from top left: A karakia timatanga (Māori: opening prayer) to welcome participants; learning more about the aims of the programme; the team at the Cawthron Aquaculture Park in Nelson; planning sampling sites around the country. Images: Cawthron Institute.

Dialogues with Industry: Harmful Algal Blooms Series Unlocks Opportunities for Innovation and Operational Services

As some harmful algal blooms (HABs) increase in frequency and severity, the need for reliable, timely, and fit-for-purpose HAB observing and mitigation services has never been greater. In response, the *Dialogues with Industry: Harmful Algal Blooms* series convened three targeted discussions in early 2025 to explore the economic dynamics and technological landscape of the HABs market sector [1–4]. The HABs Dialogues explored and defined market dynamics, identifying barriers and opportunities. The discussions focused on maturing the public/private/academic partnership, enhancing capability, and expanding capacity to

meet the growing societal need for actionable, fit-for-purpose ocean data.

Led in partnership with the Marine Technology Society’s (MTS) Ocean Enterprise Initiative, Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), the U.S. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), and the U.S. Integrated Ocean Observing System (IOOS), the Dialogues brought together stakeholders from government, academia, and industry (Fig. 1) to identify barriers, align incentives, and unlock new opportunities for innovation and operational services. Participants outlined twenty-one high priority action pathways addressing

eight cross-cutting challenges within three priority areas (Fig. 2). Action pathways aim to reduce HAB-related risks and enable a more responsive, commercially viable ecosystem for HAB detection, forecasting, and response [5].

The series emphasized the urgent need to scale capacity, incentivize public-private-academic partnerships, and highlight the return on investment for communities and sectors affected by HABs. Moving forward, recommended actions include forming dedicated working groups, recruiting new partners to help operationalize solutions, fostering increased exchanges and partnerships between public and private sectors, and building broader awareness of the economic and public health consequences tied to insufficient HAB monitoring and control.

The five reports and three recordings from the *Dialogues with*

Fig. 1. (Top) Sectors represented by the participants and observers in the three HAB Dialogues and (bottom) geographic reach of the Dialogues [5].

Fig. 2. Key outcomes of the HABs discussions, aimed at reducing HAB-related risks and enabling a more responsive, commercially viable ecosystem for HAB detection, forecasting, and response. Twenty-one high-priority action pathways were identified with the eight cross-cutting challenges they address under three priority areas: Improving the Marketplace, Collaboration to Grow and Impact Change, and Shaping the Future. The three priority areas map directly to the Dialogues with Industry Roadmap [5, 6].

Industry: Harmful Algal Blooms series will be published the week of May 19, 2025, on the [Ocean Enterprise Initiative Publications website](#). This milestone reflects a year of collaborative effort to advance data services, technology applications, and a more resilient HABs market sector. The reports are intended to be a resource for the Ocean Enterprise to focus future discussions and begin or continue the work to advance HAB observing, downstream information services, and control initiatives. The success of this effort will require continued support, interest and commitment to making the pathways effective and impactful across the private sector, government, and scientific communities.

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A decade of Pacific Salmon Foundation (PSF) Citizen Science Oceanography Monitoring Program

Ten years ago, in 2015, the Pacific Salmon Foundation (PSF) launched the Citizen Science Oceanography Program (CSOP) to address critical data gaps identified by the Salish Sea Marine Survival Project (SSMSP) [1], a multimillion-dollar international research effort involving over 60 organizations working to understand factors limiting salmon and steelhead survival in the Salish Sea. The SSMSP found that bottom-up processes (i.e., environmental conditions and prey availability) were some of the key factors affecting juvenile salmon survival [2], yet the oceanographic data needed to fully assess these factors were lacking. In response, CSOP was created to fill these gaps through systematic, long-term monitoring. The program was inspired by the vision of Dr. Eddy Carmack and developed with input and support from Fisheries and Oceans Canada (DFO) and Ocean Networks Canada. The program engaged volunteers, organized into crews on 7–10 vessels, conducting regular surveys (~20 times a year) across ~55 stations in the Strait of Georgia. With technical support from PSF, ONC, DFO, and the Universities of

Victoria (UVic) and British Columbia (UBC), the program leveraged coastal community engagement to advance data collection at an unprecedented scale. In 2016, its work was *endorsed by GlobalHAB [3]*, a collaborative initiative supported by the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) and the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO.

To ensure high data quality, CSOP separated data collection from analysis, with trained citizen scientists focusing on standardized sample collection (Figures 1-2) while experts handled processing and validation. These volunteers, all locals with a deep connection to the waters they monitored, collected oceanographic samples under regular oversight by a PSF biologist, and professional scientists analyzed the samples to ensure high research standards. While their fuel costs and mileage were covered, volunteers received only a small stipend, reinforcing their role as dedicated contributors rather than paid staff. This model fostered long-term engagement, with volunteers consistently sampling the same

locations, ensuring valuable continuity in the dataset. The data are hosted on the PSF Marine Data Center [4], making it widely accessible for research and policy use.

Throughout its ten-year history, CSOP achieved success through volunteer dedication and a commitment to scientific excellence. The team collected over 60,000 samples, including approximately 10,000 CTD casts, collected over 12,000 nutrient samples and 14,000 phytoplankton samples for harmful algae identification and enumeration, along with 2,400 chlorophyll measurements, 20,000 Secchi depth readings, 600 zooplankton samples, and over 300 biotoxin samples. CSOP crews travelled approximately 80,000 kms over 1,400 vessel trips!

Harmful algae monitoring generated the first multi-year, high-resolution dataset on harmful algal distribution and environmental conditions in the Strait of Georgia. The data revealed significant interannual variability in phytoplankton dynamics and bloom patterns, identifying key environmental drivers such as nutrient availability, stratification, and turbulence [5]. These findings enhance our understanding of regional ecological conditions that promote harmful algal blooms and provide valuable insights into their potential impacts on marine food webs and fish populations.

The dataset serves as a critical resource for future research and management efforts, with harmful algae data provided to the Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS) and Canadian Integrated Ocean Observing System (CIOOS) [6] to support broader scientific research and policy development.

Beyond data collection, CSOP made significant contributions to scientific research and public awareness. Findings were published in peer-reviewed journals, annual DFO's State of the Pacific Ocean reports [7], and the Digital Atlas of Oceanographic Conditions in the Strait of Georgia [8]. The program also produced a variety of outreach materials, including interactive story maps, reports, newsletters [9], and social media content [10].

After ten successful years, the CSOP is in its final year of monitoring. PSF is proud to have played a catalytic role in

We thank Citizen Scientists
for collecting data and samples
and being good stewards of your waters

Fig. 1. PSF Citizen Scientists.

Fig. 2. Final PSF Citizen Science Oceanography Monitoring Program Symposium, 2025.

launching and sustaining this unique long-term dataset, which now stands as a legacy to inform future research and conservation efforts. As the monitoring chapter has ended, the program's comprehensive environmental dataset, including harmful algae trends, oceanographic conditions, and zooplankton dynamics, will continue to inform critical research, conservation strategies, and management decisions, shaping marine research and policy for years to come.

While CSOP's full-scale monitoring concludes, funding from DFO's Ocean Contribution Fund will support a limited number of patrols in 2025, focusing on high-priority stations in the Strait of Georgia to ensure continued oceanographic and plankton data collection for marine conservation and climate change research. As part of this effort, environmental DNA (eDNA) sampling will be integrated to enhance biodiversity monitoring and species detection, further strengthening conservation efforts. The collected data will contribute to marine protected area (MPA) planning, resilience assessments,

and stakeholder-driven conservation initiatives.

None of this would have been possible without the dedication of the citizen scientists, who generously gave their time. Motivated by a shared commitment to science and stewardship, volunteers contributed to understanding the Salish Sea and supporting salmon populations. Their passion, commitment, and deep connection to the marine environment have left a lasting impact, helping to advance our understanding of the Strait of Georgia and shape future conservation efforts. PSF is profoundly grateful for their contributions and the legacy they have built.

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Echoes from the Bloom

BLOOMS is an art-science exhibition and VR experience that explores the occurrence of Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) as a signal of the shifting relationship between human activity and aquatic ecosystems.

Phytoplankton are key in maintaining the equilibrium on Earth. Tiny but mighty, phytoplankton produce more than half of the Earth's atmospheric oxygen and are foundational to aquatic ecosystems. However, these life-sustaining organisms often contain toxins and have the potential to form blooms that can harm aquatic ecosystems and human health. Rising sea surface temperatures and nutrient pollution exacerbate the threat of HABs.

The BLOOMS art-science exhibition (Fig. 1) highlights cosmopolitan phytoplankton and HABs occurrences in Southeast Asia, the Mediterranean, the Baltic Sea, and Brandenburg (Germany). The exhibition sheds light on the bioluminescent phytoplankton *Noctiluca scintillans* (Fig. 2), due to its visually stunning yet potentially harmful nature. *Noctiluca scintillans* blooms can cause oxygen depletion,

resulting in fish kills [1, 2]. The BLOOMS art-science exhibition reveals the paradox of nature's beauty entangled with ecological risk.

The art-science collaboration dives deep into the ethnography of marine scientists and how they monitor blooms. The volumetric data of multi-parametric sondes is sonified into an orchestral soundscape that accompanies a multi-sensorial VR experience where one dives into the microscopic world of phytoplankton. Simulating the invisible wildfires of marine heatwaves that trigger HABs, BLOOMS VR bridges the disconnect between scientific knowledge and emotional engagement for public awareness.

To extend this engagement, a citizen science workshop invited participants to learn about the basic morphology of plankton and examine field samples from Berlin's waterways under the microscope. Berlin's Lake Müggelsee is known to bloom with the cyanobacterium *Microcystis* sp. in the warm summer months [3]. *Microcystis* sp. produces microcystins, a class of hepatotoxins. Participants used a rapid

Fig. 2. Bioluminescent phytoplankton agitated with a magnetic stirrer.

test kit to detect microcystins in the water samples (Fig. 3).

BLOOMS is being held at Tier-anatomisches Theater, Berlin from 9 May to 28 June 2025, and is scheduled to be held at BASE Milano, Milan from 9 October to 22 October 2025 as part of the *ReSilence* exhibition by EU S+T+ARTS, Farout Festival 2025.

Fig. 1. Vitrine on Measuring Blooms: Apparatus for an informed sea.

Acknowledgements

BLOOMS was co-created by the artists Wendy Chua, Joyce Koh, and Gustavo Maggio, in partnership with VR developer PlayersJourney in Berlin. The art-science research was in collaboration with Sandric Leong and Team HABs from the Tropical Marine Science Institute (National University of Singapore). BLOOMS is commissioned by the EU S+T+ARTS Artist Residency *ReSilence*, funded by the EU S+T+ARTS, DFG.

The exhibition in the Tieranatomisches Theater in Berlin is supported by the research Cluster of Excellence Matters of Activity (Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin), where the BLOOMS: Citizen Science Workshop was co-run with Dr Viola Liebich from the Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries.

Fig. 3. Participant immersed in VR experience.

Fig. 4. Participant reflections.

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Fig. 5. Citizen science workshop participants examining field samples.

Fig. 6. Citizen science workshop participants conducting test for microcystins.

Enhancing Regional Efforts to Address Harmful Algal Blooms – Key Recommendations from IOCARIBE XVIII

The 18th Biennial Meeting of the UNESCO-IOC Sub-Commission for the Caribbean and Adjacent Regions (IOCARIBE) took place in Brasilia, Brazil, from April 23 to 25, 2025. The hybrid-format meeting, which welcomed both in-person and virtual participants (Fig. 1), focused on fostering international collaboration and advancing scientific research and capacity-building programs across the Tropical Americas and Caribbean (TAC) region.

IOCARIBE has, for over five decades, played a pivotal role in coordinating and promoting marine science, research, and services in the region, involving member states in addressing shared

challenges. This meeting showcased the significant strides made in tackling these challenges through the concerted efforts of working groups of local experts.

A major highlight of the session was the discussion on the progress and ongoing challenges related to Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs), as presented by the IOCARIBE-ANCA Group. The group emphasized its growing role in advancing data collection and analysis, as well as training initiatives to improve regional responses to HABs. Despite these successes, the meeting acknowledged the substantial ecological and socio-economic impacts

of HABs on the region, particularly on the tourism sector.

In response, IOCARIBE issued several key recommendations to strengthen the ongoing efforts of the ANCA Group:

- **Coordinated Monitoring and Response Systems:** IOCARIBE highlighted the importance of strengthening the regional monitoring network and ensuring the integration of data into the IOC-UNESCO HAEDAT platform. This effort aims to improve the capacity to detect and analyze HABs and marine stressors.
- **International Partnerships:** The invaluable collaboration with the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) was acknowledged for its role in enhancing regional capabilities. These initiatives focus on strengthening the region's

Fig. 1. IOCARIBE XVIII Participants.

ability to monitor HABs and other environmental stressors.

- **Training and Workshops:** A key recommendation was the coordination of regional training courses and workshops to focus on the implementation of HAB monitoring, early warning system development, and data analysis. These will include virtual training opportunities to increase accessibility.
- **Regional Awareness Campaigns:** The meeting stressed the need to raise awareness of the socio-economic impacts of ciguatera and other marine biotoxin syndromes, particularly their detrimental effects on the tourism industry.
- **Strengthening National Focal Points:** The President of IOCARIBE urged member states to designate or confirm ANCA National Focal Points to ensure timely and effective national reporting. Member States were also encouraged to facilitate cross-sectoral collaboration, particularly between environmental, health, and tourism authorities, to mitigate risks associated with marine biotoxins.
- **Expanding the ANCA Network:** The ongoing expansion of the ANCA network was identified as a critical strategy for improving the effectiveness of regional early warning systems for HABs.

Moving Forward: ANCA's Expanded Role

- **Broader Stakeholder Engagement:** Engaging local communities, the private sector, and academic institutions in monitoring and awareness programs to ensure that all sectors are informed and actively involved in addressing HABs.
- **Incorporating Indigenous Knowledge:** Integrating indigenous and local knowledge into monitoring systems to enhance understanding and early detection of environmental changes.
- **Incentivizing Regular Reporting:** Introducing a system of recognition and rewards for countries and organizations that consistently contribute valuable data to the ANCA network, ensuring that the network remains robust and active.

These additional measures aim to expand the scope of ANCA's impact and deepen the regional collaboration necessary to mitigate the challenges posed by HABs and their broader environmental consequences. By strengthening partnerships, enhancing data sharing, and investing in capacity building, IOCARIBE aims to empower the region to better respond to these critical environmental issues.

These recommendations reflect IOCARIBE's commitment to fostering a collaborative approach in addressing the challenges posed by harmful algal blooms and to improving the resilience of the Tropical Americas and Caribbean region to these environmental threats. By strengthening partnerships, enhancing data sharing, and investing in capacity building, IOCARIBE aims to empower the region to better respond to these critical environmental issues.

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Call for Proposals: Assessing the Link between Eutrophication and HABs in Coastal Areas Through the Development and Application of Isotopic Techniques

The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) supports Member States in addressing pressing environmental challenges through its Coordinated Research Projects (CRPs). CRPs are collaborative, multi-year research efforts that leverage nuclear and isotopic science to address global issues ranging from climate change to marine pollution. This new CRP investigates the complex interplay between nutrient enrichment and the frequency and severity of Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) in coastal areas.

Characterized by the rapid growth of algae, HABs can have a wide variety of negative impacts on ecosystems and human health and represent a growing socio-ecological global concern [1–2].

To be clear, HABs are not “one-size-fits-all”; there are many different species (e.g., dinoflagellates, haptophytes, diatoms, cyanobacteria, raphidophytes and dictyochophytes) which may or may not produce biotoxins. Those that do produce biotoxins can bioaccumulate in marine organisms and cause hazardous foodborne illnesses such as shellfish or ciguatera poisoning, whereas those that do not produce biotoxins can still negatively impact water quality and oxygen levels [3]. Both toxic and non-toxic HABs can lead to habitat destruction and economic damages to fisheries, tourism, and the recreation sector.

The frequency and severity of HABs are closely linked to eutrophication —

the excessive accumulation of biomass following enrichment of water bodies with nutrients, primarily nitrogen and phosphorus from terrestrial inputs [4–5]. Agricultural runoff, wastewater discharge, and industrial pollution all contribute to excess nutrient levels in coastal waters, creating favorable conditions for algal growth. Local hydrodynamics, biotic interactions or nutrient speciation (inorganic vs. organic) and nutrient ratios (N, P, Si) also control HABs dynamics. The consequences of global and climate change (e.g., marine heat waves, extreme weather events, sea level rise, increased shipping activities and coastal use) add to local pressures. However, the relative contribution of

Fig. 1. Consultation meeting for the conceptualisation of this CRP held in April 2025 at the IAEA Marine Environment Laboratory (IAEA-MEL), Monaco. From left to right: **Top row:** Hugo Berthelot, Carlos Alonso, Philipp Hess, Valentí Rodellas Vila, Jennifer McKay. **Bottom row:** Beata Szymczycha, Andreas Musolff, Elias Dimitriou, Jana Friedrich, Kristof Möller. **Participants missing from the photo:** Marie-Yasmine Bottein and Mélanie Vital.

local pressures, as well as global and climate changes, to eutrophication and the frequency and severity of HABs remains largely unaddressed.

This CRP contributes to closing this knowledge gap, which is crucial for the management and mitigation of the adverse impacts of HABs.

Through this CRP, the IAEA will support the development, refinement, and application of nuclear and isotopic techniques to assist Member States in assessing the link between Eutrophication and HABs in Coastal Areas. This will provide actionable knowledge to assess nutrient pollution and its sources in coastal zones for the management programs of the Member States. This CRP is intended to be complementary to CRP F33030, which focuses on the development and application of isotopic techniques to assess nutrient fluxes from land to sea, and applications to one or both CRPs are possible.

The overall objective is to disentangle the role of land-to-sea nutrient fluxes in coastal eutrophication fostering the formation of HABs and biotoxins, in the light of climate and global change and other environmental drivers. This objective contributes to the development of mitigation measures to combat the impacts of HABs on seafood safety, water quality, coastal community health, and tourism. This Coordinated Research Project (CRP) will directly

contribute to Targets 2 and 14.1 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which aim to reduce food insecurity and prevent and significantly reduce marine pollution of all kinds, with a particular focus on land-based activities, including nutrient inputs and their detrimental impacts.

Furthermore, this CRP aims to achieve several specific objectives to enhance our understanding and management of HABs in the context of coastal eutrophication. A key goal is to identify and characterize the main abiotic drivers — such as physicochemical conditions — as well as biotic influences, including grazing, viral lysis, and allelopathy, that contribute to the development of HABs. This will be accomplished through the application of advanced isotopic techniques. In parallel, the project seeks to deepen our knowledge of the biosynthesis, accumulation, and trophic transfer of algal toxins within marine ecosystems using nuclear and isotopic methods. To understand the evolution of these phenomena over time, the CRP will also focus on reconstructing past relationships between eutrophication and HABs by analysing sedimentary cyst records in relation to anthropogenic environmental changes. Finally, the project places strong emphasis on the effective dissemination of research findings to relevant stakeholders and the broader scientific community,

ensuring that generated knowledge contributes directly to policy and coastal management strategies.

Acknowledgements

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SCIENTIFIC HIGHLIGHTS

Scientific Highlights is a new section in *Harmful Algae News* dedicated to showcasing cutting-edge research that opens fresh avenues in our understanding of harmful algae. These short contributions aim to spotlight innovative methods, surprising discoveries, or new perspectives that could reshape how we approach the field. In this first instalment, we feature a striking example of the potential of transcriptomic tools to unravel complex ecological and toxicological processes. We hope this inspires future submissions that bring to light similarly bold and forward-looking work. If you're pushing boundaries — however briefly — we'd love to hear from you!

Genetic markers enable early prediction of toxic *Pseudo-nitzschia* algal blooms

A recent groundbreaking study on predicting *Pseudo-nitzschia* harmful algal blooms (HABs) in the California Current Ecosystem has uncovered molecular predictors for domoic acid events that rapidly detect toxin production before harmful impacts occur. The Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences (PNAS) publication, "*Molecular forecasting of domoic acid during a pervasive toxic diatom bloom* [1]," details new insights on the mechanisms that drive some *Pseudo-nitzschia* species to produce the neurotoxin domoic acid (DA). Toxic *Pseudo-nitzschia* species occur globally (Fig. 1), causing amnesic shellfish poisoning (ASP) in humans and DA toxicosis in marine mammals and other wildlife. HAEDAT records indicate DA events have increased across the U.S. overall and impact the U.S. West Coast almost annually [2]. The 2015 U.S. West Coast *Pseudo-nitzschia* HAB and related DA event resulted in significant cultural and socioeconomic disruption, including \$100 million in lost revenue to the West Coast commercial Dungeness crab and razor clam fisheries [3].

Key findings of the study include:

- Co-expression of the DA biosynthesis gene *dabA* and the silica transporter gene *sit1* served as a robust predictor of DA production one week in advance of observed *Pseudo-nitzschia* bloom toxicity in water samples collected from April to September 2015.
- Iron and silica co-limitation

were identified as factors that characterized the bloom and likely promoted toxin production.

- Increasing iron limitation, likely associated with ocean acidification, may play a previously unrecognized role in driving *Pseudo-nitzschia* bloom frequency and toxicity.

This molecular framework for forecasting DA-producing HABs offers a tool for early warning systems to mitigate public health risks and economic impacts. The findings underscore the importance of monitoring genetic markers to predict and manage the occurrence of toxic HABs. The research also highlights the role of nutrient stress, particularly iron and silica limitations, in influencing bloom dynamics and toxicity.

The 2015 West Coast *Pseudo-nitzschia* HAB and related domoic acid event was the largest HAB recorded in the Northeast Pacific. During this event, researchers collected water samples from Monterey Bay on a near-weekly basis, recording the nutrient and domoic acid concentration data that were used in this study [4, 5]. Molecular and transcriptional characterization was performed using 18S and ITS2 metabarcoding combined with polyA-enriched RNA sequencing. This approach allowed for the identification of active transcription of DA biosynthesis genes and the assessment of gene expression patterns associated

with toxin production [1, 6].

The integration of molecular techniques to monitor gene expression offers a promising approach for the early detection and forecasting of toxic *Pseudo-nitzschia* HAB events. By identifying genetic markers predictive of DA production, this research provides valuable insights for developing effective HAB monitoring and management strategies. This is the first report of forecasting a toxic HAB event using molecular diagnostic tools, and will hopefully provide the basis for future early bloom toxicity warnings that can prevent harm to public health and local economies along the U.S. West Coast and around the globe.

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Fig. 1 (A). The occurrence of *Pseudo-nitzschia* is plotted based on observations recorded by the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS). The localization of ASP events reported in HAEDAT since 1987 is highlighted in red circles, with the size of the circle corresponding to the number of reported events in a given region [7]. (B). The metatranscriptomic model where the expression of *sit1* and *dabA* can predict domoic acid a week in advance of HAB impacts [1, 7]. Figure permission for use: <https://www.pnas.org/author-center/publication-charges/standard-pnas-license-terms>

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30th Anniversary of the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae at the University of Copenhagen, Denmark

On 5 May 1995, the Executive Secretary of the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (IOC), Gunnar Kullenberg, officially opened the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae at the Department of Biology, Marine Biological Section of the University of Copenhagen (UCPH), Denmark.

The establishment of HAB Programme activity centres was proposed at the Twenty-fifth Session of the IOC Executive Council (Paris 10–18 March 1992), and the idea was further elaborated at the First Session of the IOC-FAO Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB, 23–25 June 1992). At the Seventeenth Session of the IOC Assembly (Paris, 25 February–11 March, 1993), Denmark offered to host and establish a Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae. The main purpose of the Centre is to provide the framework for systematic assistance in training and capacity building to developing countries with respect to harmful algae

We celebrated 30 years of the Centre on 5 May 2025. Over this period, the focus of the activities of the Centre has shifted to reflect developments in the

priorities of the IOC-FAO IPHAB.

The systematic assistance in training and capacity building with respect to harmful algae, including supporting the International Phytoplankton Intercalibration (IPI), is today integrated into the IOC Ocean Teacher Global Academy (OTGA). Training courses held at or by the Centre have provided opportunities to hundreds of trainees over the 30 years.

The Centre also serves as a decentralized programme office for the HAB-related projects implemented by the Ocean Science Section of the IOC and a support office for the IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB international science programme. As such it has been instrumental in supporting implementation of IPHAB work plans including the development of the IOC UNESCO GlobalHAB Status Report and the Harmful Algal Information System. It is staffed by Mr. Henrik Enevoldsen, Head of Centre (IOC), and Associate Professor Dr. Jacob Larsen (UCPH), with Professor Dr. Per Juel-Hansen and Professor Dr. Øjvind Moestrup as the focal points to the Centre at the Department of Biology.

The partnership between the IOC

Fig. 2. IOC Executive Secretary Gunnar Kullenberg speaking at the opening of the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae in Copenhagen on 5 May 1995.

and the University in the Centre was expanded to include the Danish Natural History Museum (SNM) in April 2013 to allow for Professor Dr. Nina Lundholm, to assist in capacity development activities and to develop joint projects to implement the IOC HAB programme, in particular the IOC UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Toxic Micro Algae (a section of the World Register of Marine Organisms WoRMS). The Taxonomic Reference List provides a reference for the use of names and information on each species of toxic microalgae.

The Centre has recently expanded its scope to facilitate additional programmatic work of the Ocean Science Section of IOC and is implementing a project focused on establishing a proof of concept in relation to the impacts on marine life of ocean acidification.

The Centre is a successful example of the value and benefits from long-standing IOC partnerships with, and in-kind funding by, Member States and their institutions.

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Fig. 1. IOC Executive Secretary Gunnar Kullenberg and Professor Øjvind Moestrup opening the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae on 5 May 1995.

Call for ICHA bids: Bring ICHA 2029 to your region!

We are pleased to announce a call for bids for the **23rd International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA) in 2029**. The ICHA is organized every two years and brings together harmful algae experts from around the world. It is co-convened by the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA).

ICHA conferences are known for their high quality, vibrant interactions, and great fun. They are supported by an extensive HAB community covering a range of HAB taxa and habitats, with excellent science ranging from the basics of HAB physiology, genetics, toxins and ecology to predictions and management of associated risks.

Organizing an ICHA is a great opportunity to highlight HAB science in your region, bring together the international HAB community with local and regional stakeholders, and showcase regional HAB research to

a global audience. As ISSHA, we offer support in organizing the scientific program, overall promotion, additional events (auction, workshops), and various travel support schemes.

The conference has a tradition of “continent-hopping” to reflect the global interest in HABS and to allow different regions to attract this periodic science inventory event. With the conference being held in South America (Chile) in 2025 and Europe (Aberdeen, UK) in 2027, bids for 2029 from North America, Africa, or the Australasian region would be particularly welcome.

It should be noted that three to four years of preparation is typically needed for organizing this conference. While the financial risk is carried by the organizer, ISSHA supports all conference organizers by providing information on sponsors and other useful financial details from previous editions.

Bid documents presenting the venue and the organizing institution(s) are expected prior to the conference in Chile, where they will be presented. If there are multiple bids, ISSHA members will vote on the selection.

Please contact Dedmer Van de Waal (ISSHA President; d.vandewaal@nioo.knaw.nl) by **June 20 at the latest** if you are considering a bid and/or have any questions.

New deadline
for abstract submission and
early bird registration for the
ICHA 2025 meeting is
June 15th

<https://icha2025.org/abstracts-topics/>

PUNTA ARENAS - CHILE 2025

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ICHIRO IMAI

In Memoriam (1953 – 2025)

Professor Ichiro Imai (6 January 1953 – 21 April 2025) was a leading researcher on Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) in Japan. He passed away on 21 April 2025 due to pancreatic cancer. He dedicated more than 40 years of his life to HAB research, focusing on red tide mitigation, and remained active in conferences and academic events until shortly before his passing. Initially, his work focused on understanding and predicting the mechanisms behind red tide occurrences. In the later stages of his career, his attention shifted to developing prevention strategies. His primary objective was to create environmentally friendly control methods against HABs to reduce the hardships faced by fishermen.

Ichiro earned his Ph.D. in Agricultural Science from Kyoto University in 1989. In 1980, he joined the Nansei National Research Institute, Fisheries Agency of Japan. He moved to Kyoto University in 1994, and then to Hokkaido University in 2009, where he continued his work as Professor Emeritus from 2018 until 2025. His studies broadly encompassed the life cycles of microalgae, the physiology and ecology of harmful algae, and mitigation strategies for HABs. Ichiro served as the chair of the Seto Inland Sea Wide Area Fisheries Coordination Committee (Fisheries Agency), and the Osaka Sea Area Fisheries Adjustment Commission (Osaka Prefecture). His research included studies on the life cycle strategies of the fish-killing raphidophytes *Chattonella* and *Heterosigma akashiwo* in temperate coastal seas, and their bloom dynamics related to their life cycle, cyst physiology, and seed-population dynamics. He also investigated the biological control of HABs by promoting the growth of nutrient-competing diatoms through artificial perturbation and sediment lifting in coastal seas. Applications conducted in Osaka Bay between 2020 and 2023 successfully suppressed blooms of *Alexandrium*. In his final years, he focused on preventing HABs using algicidal bacteria inhabiting the surfaces of seaweeds and seagrasses.

Through this work, he championed the restoration of seaweed and seagrass beds were environmentally friendly biological control methods for HABs.

Internationally, he contributed significantly to HAB science as a committee member of the HAB section of the North Pacific Marine Science Organization (PICES) from 2000 to 2019. Ichiro was a Council member of the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) from 2008–2012 and 2016–2025. In November 2023, he chaired the 20th International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA) in Hiroshima, which gathered researchers from around the world. He received numerous honours throughout his career, including the Achievement Award for Young Scientist in Fisheries Science from the Japanese Society of Fisheries Science (1992), the Japanese Society of Fisheries Science Award from the Japanese Society of Fisheries Science, the Marine Biology Contribution Award at the 3rd Asian Marine Biology Symposium (2017), an Academic Award from the Japanese Society of Phycology (2021), the Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award, International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (2023), and was recognized as a Harmful Algal Bloom Trailblazer by ISSHA (2023). His colleagues remember him as a profoundly intelligent man, deeply knowledgeable in his field, yet always humble and with a wonderful sense of humour. We extend our sympathy to his family, friends, and colleagues.

Ichiro also supervised many

students over the course of his career, including undergraduate, Master's (44), Ph.D. students (11), and thesis Ph.D. students (7) —mentoring over 100 students in total in the study of harmful algae s during his approximately 40-year career. He was once quoted as saying, “I have a great job and am blessed with the opportunity to do exciting research, supported by a long list of smart, talented, and hard-working students and collaborators. My successes are theirs as well.”

His major publications include:

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(A) Ichiro sampling sea grass in Puget Sound, Washington State USA; Relaxing with PICES colleagues: (B) with Nobuharu Inaba (center) and Professor Watanabe (right) and (C) with Vera Trainer at the PICES conference in Nanaimo, BC, Canada.

(D) ICHA20 was held in Hiroshima, Japan on 2023, and Imai was the Chair of the Local Organizing Committee. (E) Opening remarks from the Chair. (F) Awarded with the Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award. Presentation ceremony with Professor Yasumoto handing out the prize and Don Anderson on the left. (G) Finally relaxed during the performance for participants at the Gala dinner.

(H) Last meeting with the Council members of the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA), Hiroshima, 2023.

GEORGINA LEMBEYE

In Memoriam (1948 – 2024)

Georgina Lembeye Valdivia held degrees in Biology and as a Professor of Biology from the Universidad Católica de Valparaíso. She devoted herself to the study of harmful algal blooms (HABs) and their impacts on public health and aquaculture in Chile, particularly through her work at the Patagonian Institute. She published papers on the biology and toxicology of *Alexandrium catenella* (formerly *Gonyaulax catenella*), responsible for severe Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP) events in Chilean Patagonia. During the 1980s, she participated in reporting intoxications after consumption of contaminated shellfish from the Reloncaví Estuary in Los Lagos Region, Chile. Her work enabled the establishment of a correlation between these events and the presence of the dinoflagellate *Dinophysis acuta*, associated with diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP) outbreaks in Chile. Georgina presented these findings to the international HAB Community at the ICHA conferences and their proceedings; a detailed overview of shellfish poisoning events, suspected causative agents and their impacts in Southern Chile was published in the IOC Workshop Report of the second regional meeting of South American HAB experts.

In 1988, following the devastating salmon mortality caused by a brown tide (“marea café”) of *Heterosigma akashiwo*, in northern Patagonia, she was part of the team that designed and implemented the Phytoplankton Monitoring Programme for the salmon industry. A tireless and independent researcher, Georgina carried out her field monitoring activities under challenging conditions at remote stations near salmon farms. This programme was presented by Alejandro Clément at the 5th ICHA Conference in Rhode Island, USA, 1991.

In the 1990s, she reported the first observation of *A. catenella*—until then limited to the southernmost regions XI and XII—in qualitative analyses of water samples collected off the southern coasts of the Chiloé Archipelago (Region X). She also led various projects monitoring the presence of toxins in

filter-feeding molluscs and gastropods in Aysén (Region XI). Together with Alejandro Clément, Georgina was a founding member of international working groups such as the IOC-FANSA (Floraciones Algas Nocivas en Sudamérica). Nationally, she contributed to the Working Group on HABs of the Chilean National Oceanographic Committee (CONA).

In 2000, she joined the Undersecretariat of Fisheries and Aquaculture (SUBPESCA), expanding her focus to

include Invasive Alien Species and participating in the implementation of the *Regulation on Hydrobiological Pests (REPLA)*, the *Permanent HAB/Red Tides Monitoring Programme*, and the *Didymo* monitoring programme. After an outstanding and impactful career, she retired from SUBPESCA in December 2013. Georgina was a thorough and responsible professional, leaving an invaluable legacy in the knowledge and monitoring of HABs in Southern Chile.

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Chilean and foreign researchers visiting Angelmó Bay, Puerto Montt, in September 1989. From left to right, front row: FJR (Max) Taylor, Tomotoshi Okaichi and Georgina Lembeye; back row: Eugenio Larraín, Tim Wyatt, Alberto Labbé, Alejandro Clément and Adolfo Alvial. Photo Courtesy of A. Clément.

New Chair of the IPHAB Task Team on HAIS/GHSR

Maarten De Rijcke, a marine biologist at the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ) in Belgium, has been appointed Chair of the IPHAB Task Team on the Harmful Algal Information System (HAIS) and the Global HAB Status Report (GHSR). His current research is focused on sea spray aerosols, and the potential for phycotoxins and bacterial endotoxins to become airborne and affect human health. Since 2017, he served

as Belgium's national HAEDAT editor and national delegate to IPHAB. Maarten will support the reworking of HAEDAT and the finalization of HAIS. Based in the same building as the IODE Secretariat, Maarten looks forward to engaging with the global HAB community to strengthen these information systems and support their continued scientific and operational value.

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